

Studies in Terpenes. Part XVI. On the Comparative Behaviour of α - and β -Pinenes towards Maleic Anhydride

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α -Pinene and β -pinene on interaction with maleic anhydride isomerise to a mixture of *p*-menthadienes and camphene, the β -isomer being more reactive than the α -isomer. The reaction leading to limonene is shown to be faster than that to camphene. There is also superficial aromatisation to *p*- and *o*-cymenes. A mechanism is proposed to account for the various transformations encountered in this study.

Hultsch¹⁻² reported that α -pinene (I) slowly incorporated maleic anhydride (II) to form an adduct of undetermined structure and also superficially decyclised to α -phellandrene which then underwent the normal diene synthesis. As regards β -pinene (III), the only investigation with maleic anhydride is that of Arnold and Showell.³ In boiling xylene, β -pinene absorbed maleic anhydride by a concerted mechanism, introducing a new asymmetric centre and with simultaneous formation of the two diastereoisomers of 10-pinen-2-yl-succinic anhydride; α -pinene did not react under these conditions. Further to our studies on the action of maleic anhydride on various terpenes⁴, we have now examined the behaviour of α - and β -pinenes. The results are recorded in Tables IA and IB

On refluxing an equimolecular mixture of α -pinene and maleic anhydride for 6 hours at 150-75°, dipentene(IV), terpinolene(V), α -terpinene(VI), camphene(VII), *p*-cymene(VIII), and *o*-cymene(IX) were obtained (Reaction 1). On the other hand, β -pinene at 160-265° but in otherwise identical conditions gave (VI) and (VII) in addition to (VIII) and (IX) (Reaction 8). In contrast to (I), (III) reacted completely. On increasing the refluxing period to 10 hours, α -pinene was, however, transformed in a manner analogous to β -pinene (Reaction 2). The expulsion of succinic anhydride in reactions (2) and (8) is noteworthy. Of singular interest is the difference in the behaviour of (III) with temperature as shown by reactions (8) and (9). The reaction at the lower temperature gave (—)-limonene (X), (IV), (V), (VI), (VIII), and (IX); unchanged α -pinene was also present.

In order to obtain additional information, a series of reactions was carried out, keeping the molar ratio of the pinene (α or β) to maleic anhydride (II) as 1:2. No isomer was found when α -pinene was allowed to stand with (II) in acetone solution at 35° for 1 hour (Reaction 3). A similar treatment of β -pinene, however, resulted in (X), (IV), (VI) (traces), (VIII), and (IX); there was no indication of the presence of (V) (Reaction 10). When (III) was refluxed with (II) in acetone solution at 75-76°, (X), (IV), (V), (VIII), and (IX) were formed (Reaction 11).

1. *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1173.

2. Cf. Bhargava and Haksar, *Perf. Essent. Oil Rec.*, 1962, 53, 379.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 419.

4. Sugathan and Verghese, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 91.

With the exclusion of acetone, β -pinene faintly reacted by a 2-hr. heating at $75^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ and gave rise to traces of (VI) (Reaction 13). At this temperature, even by a 6-hr. heating, α -pinene was substantially unaffected (Reaction 6), whereas β -pinene reacted completely; the products from β -pinene included (X), (IV), (V), (VI), (VIII), and (IX) (Reaction 14). A general feature of this series of reactions was that β -pinene suffered scission of the cyclobutane ring to yield mainly *p*-menthadienes; the competitive rearrangement to (VII) was not observed.

In all the reactions studied, we could not recognise the interconversion of α - and β -pinenes⁵.

Though no attempt has been made to isolate the products of addition, which may arise by the participation of (I) and (III) or their *para*- and *ortho*-⁶ menthadiene isomers, it is of interest to point out that pyrolysis of the crude adducts from reactions (1), (2), and (8) furnished (VIII) and (IX) along with succinic anhydride⁴.

Thus, several processes occurred when α - and β -pinenes reacted with maleic anhydride. These were (i) isomerisation by ring cleavage to optically active and inactive *p*-menthadienes; (ii) Wagner-Meerwein rearrangement to (VII); (iii) aromatisation to (VIII) and (IX) and probably (iv) addition.

The process (i) was mainly confined to yield *p*-isomers by way of fission of the C₁-C₆ bond in α - and β -pinenes. Nevertheless, the breaking of the C₃-C₆ bond, leading to *o*-isomers, cannot be ruled out since otherwise it would be difficult to explain the formation of (IX).

The question naturally arises as to what are the primary *p*-menthadienes derivable from α - and β -pinenes. From the frequency of occurrence of (IV) and/or (X) among reaction products, it may be inferred that limonene is the major initial decyclisation product. Further, the concurrent presence of (V) and (VI) with (IV) and/or (X) (Reactions 1, 9, and 14) can be interpreted by the following isomerisation sequence: (IV) or (X) $\rightarrow$ (V) $\rightarrow$ (VI) which has been shown to be operative and outlined in greater detail in an earlier communication⁷. In the case of β -pinene, the selective formation of (VI) without the intermediate (IV) and/or (X) and (V) is, however, intriguing (Reaction 13). This means that (VI) can stem from β -pinene independent of other *p*-menthadienes. An isomerisation of this type was not detected with α -pinene.

Camphene (VII) is yet another hydrocarbon frequently formed in the reactions of α - and β -pinenes with maleic anhydride and must have derived directly from them.

Of the rearrangements to (IV) and/or (X) and (VII), it is specially noteworthy that the reaction leading to (IV) and/or (X) is faster than that to (VII)⁸. Only under relatively drastic conditions, isomerisation to (VII) is favoured (Reactions 1, 2, and 8)⁹. Again, with respect to the formation of *para* derivatives, the greater reactivity of β -pinene

5. Cf. Wheeler, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1020.

6. Kogima, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1957, 78, 733.

7. Sugathan and Vergheese, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 475.

8. Cf. Wystrach *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 5786.

9. Cf. Dupont, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1932, 51, 1579; Charlton and Day, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1937, 29, 92.

as compared to the α -isomer is revealed (cf. Reactions 3 and 10 & 6 and 14)^{10,11}.

From the foregoing observations we note that α - and β -pinenes differ in their response to the action of maleic anhydride. Although both the pinenes possess a double bond in conjugation with a cyclobutane ring, β -pinene is markedly more reactive than α -isomer. This superior reactivity should be attributed to the lateral CH_2 grouping in β -pinene, a conclusion which is in keeping with the fact that in 6-ring systems exocyclic double bonds¹² are far more unstable than endocyclic ones.

The cymenes (VIII and IX) are formed only in small amounts, (IX) being less than (VIII). Although the formation of (IX) testified to the cleavage of the C_5 - C_6 bond in α - and β -pinenes, we were unable to recognise its precursors, α -menthadienes. As would be explained in the sequel, on theoretical grounds the decyclisation of α - and β -pinenes to yield hydrocarbons of the α -series is a slender possibility¹³.

From this and earlier studies^{4,7,14}, we find that maleic anhydride functions as a dienophile towards terpenes with conjugated double bonds, but in cases where this structural pattern is lacking, it acts as a typical acid catalyst and causes the rearrangements, characteristic of this class of sensitive compounds. The expectation that α - and β -pinenes by virtue of a double bond in conjugation with a labile ring should act as a ψ -diene¹⁵ and participate in forced diene syntheses is not fulfilled to any appreciable extent, but addition by a concerted mechanism (*vide supra*) is a clear major possibility which, however, did not engage our attention.

Mechanism.—The C^+ ion mechanism is adequate to account most of the changes encountered in this investigation. The manner in which these ions are produced is not quite clear; there exists the possibility that traces of moisture or maleic acid, which are likely to be associated with maleic anhydride, may contribute the H^+ necessary to produce these positive fragments. The acceptance of H^+ by the polarised double bond in α - and β -pinenes results in the pinyli ion (XI) which by a β -bond splitting affords the *p*-menthenyl ion (XII), responsible for the *para* derivatives. On the other hand, the uptake of H^+ directly by the cyclobutane ring of α - and β -pinenes may result in the *a*-menthenyl ions (XIII) and (XIV) respectively and these are the precursors of *ortho* derivatives¹⁶. Of the modes of generating C^+ ions, protonation of a double bond is energetically far more favoured than the direct rupture of a four-membered ring¹⁷. Consequently, formation of (XI) is favoured and the chances of obtaining *ortho* derivatives through (XIII) and (XIV) are extremely poor, as has been observed experimentally. It is this conclusion that we also arrive at by an

10. Austerweil, *Perf., Essent. Oil Rec.*, 1925, 16, 187; Robert and Day, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1326.
11. Cf. Delepine and Adida, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1928, 39, 782; Austerweil, *ibid.*, 1924, 37, 685, 686; 1926, 39, 621, 954, 1643.
12. Brown *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 467; Fleck, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 22, 430; Brown, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 439.
13. Cf. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Vol. II, Cambridge University Press, 2nd ed., 1957, p. 237.
14. Sugathan and Verghese, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 192.
15. Alder, "Newer Methods of Preparative Organic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1948, p. 399.
16. Ipatieff and Pines, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1932; Verghese, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 155.
17. Mayo, "Mono and Sesquiterpenoids", Vol. II, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959, p. 120.

application to α - and β -pinenes of Schmidt's rule^{18,19} which states that in unsaturated hydrocarbons, bonds next to double bonds are strengthened but those following are weakened.

Whereas (XI) can stabilise by ejection of a proton, resulting in either α - or β -pinene, we are unable to detect this interconversion in any of the reactions. It is to be emphasised that if β -pinene were to rearrange initially to α -pinene, the greater reactivity of the former cannot be accounted for. A direct reaction sequence is therefore legitimate for β -pinene. We cannot exclude the reverse possibility, viz., the transformations of (I) through (III)³ although no experimental backing for this can be gathered from the present study.

A two-fold β -bond migration changes (XI) through the bornyl (XV) to the camphanyl (XVI) ion from which by loss of H⁺ camphene (VII) is obtained.

The significant finding that the reaction leading to (IV) and/or (X) is faster than that to (VII) can now be explained. To obtain (IV) and/or (X) and (VII), (XI) has to isomerise initially to a tertiary (XII) and secondary (XV) ion respectively. A fundamental postulate

18. *Ber.*, 1935, **68**, 60.

19. Oda and Nomamoto, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind., Japan*, Suppl. binding, 1932, **35**, 543.

of ionic theory is that the order of stability of C⁺ ion is as: tertiary >> secondary > primary²⁰. On this basis the rearrangement of (XI) to (XII) is to be more facile than to (XV). Hence conversion of (I) and (III) to (IV) and/or (X) must be faster than to (VII).

These interpretations consider C⁺ ions as reaction intermediates and sharply define the various steps leading to the isomers for which, however, there is no evidence²¹. It may be that full carbonium ions are not at all developed. Secondary processes come in and we get a cycle established²¹. In this theory, the introduction of a proton and its removal from another place are nearly synchronised. The formation of (VI) from β -pinene (III) is most simply represented as in (XVII) which implies that H⁺ wanders to make up the defect in C joined to Me₂. This single circuit summarises all the processes which are set forth to explain the conversion of β -pinene to (VI) according to the carbonium ion theory²². Thus, the puzzling unilateral decyclisation of (III) to (VI) without the concomitant formation of the expected intermediates (IV) and/or (X) and (V) is explained. Other isomers can also be accounted for in a similar manner.

As for (VIII) and (IX), these arise either by a hydrogen-transfer mechanism or by a decomposition of condensation products of menthadienes with maleic anhydride²³.

EXPERIMENTAL

The source, methods of isolation, and characteristics of α - and β -pinenes used in this work have been described earlier²⁴. Maleic anhydride (White label) was obtained from Eastman Kodak.

The experimental procedure, essentially the same as used in previous work^{4,7}, is presented in Table II.

The steam-volatile reaction products were fractionated and the hydrocarbons in the various cuts were identified by preparing suitable derivatives. ($\pm$)-Limonene, (—)-limonene, and terpinolene were characterised as tetrabromides^{4,25,26} and α -terpinene as nitrosite⁴. For (—)-limonene the bromination technique used for the ($\pm$)- isomer was adopted. Camphene and *p*-cymene were oxidised to camphor²⁴ and terephthalic acid²⁷ and further converted into 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones^{28,29} and dimethyl ester³⁰ respectively. *o*-Cymene was oxidised to *o*-phthalic acid³¹ which due to meagre yield could only be recognised by the

20. Whitmore, *Chem. & Eng. News*, 1948, 26, 688.

21. Cf. Robinson, *Endeavour*, 1954, 13, 173.

22. Mosher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2139.

23. For references see 4 and 7.

24. Punnoose and Verghese, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 835.

25. Barraud, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1924, 35, 830; Wallach, *Annalen*, 1888, 246, 224.

26. Verghese, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 260.

27. Xavier *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 112.

28. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1957, p. 344.

29. Janot and Mouton, *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1936, 23, 547.

30. Verghese and Veddanapalli, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12B, 122.

31. *Idem, ibid.*, 1957, 16B, 224.

fluorescence test. α -Pinene and β -pinene were identified through the nitrosochloride of m.p. 108°³² and nopinic acid of m.p. 127° respectively, following the procedure recommended by Mirov³³.

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32. Cf. Simonsen, "The Terpenes", Vol. II, Cambridge University Press, 2nd ed., 1957, p. 179.
33. Mirov, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1951, 40, 410.